

Abyssal turbulence in the vicinity of Lucky Strike

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Lucky Strike - observational site

- In the Mid Atlantic Ridge.
- Is a volcano with hydrothermal activity.
- Most diverse fauna.
- EMSO-Azores marine observatory since 2010
- Monitoring biological, chemical, geophysical and physical aspects.
- Mooring monitors the water column.

Outline and Objectives

Mooring observations

- Identify processes at Lucky Strike.
- Is there is interannual variability?

Numerical plume experiment

- Study the mechanical energy budget.
- Estimating the mixing efficiency of the plume.

Mooring observations

3 types of instruments:

RBR = Temperature SBE = CTD Aquadopp = Horizontal Current meter.

Methodology

- Compile de clean data in **netCDF** files, to be published.
- PSD estimates of temperature and HKE.
 - Welch method.
- Distributions of the current meter and the temperature, to see the variability.

Current meter

Horizontal Kinetic Energy estimates

Suggest that there is spacial variability near the sea floor.

HKE

2017 at the bottom

- There is an amplification of the internal tide at Lucky Strike.
- Both bands follow a power law.

Temperature PSD (year comparison)

- No interannual variability.
- M2 peak is predominant at both depths.
- At -800 m we see the consistent appearance of a peak at 38 cpd.

Temperature PSD (depth comparison)

- In **geostrophic eddy band** PSD is larger at -800 m to -1300 m (10 to 1 days)
- The **internal wave band** is dominated by M2 peak.
- Mysterious peak at 38 cpd, at the top of the mooring.

Mooring conclusions

- Region is dominated by internal tides.
- Spatial variability close to the seafloor.
- No interannual variation away from the seafloor.

Propositions for future campaigns

- Change mooring position in following years.
- Explore the consistent appearance of the peak at 38 cpd, between -800m to -1300m.
- Increase the spatial resolution of the current meters, would help identify the structure of passing eddies.

Plume experiment

- Stratification: $N^2 = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-2}$ • 10 days.
- Buoyancy forcing: $Q = 127 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ • Resolution 32x64x64 (2000 m x 4000m x 4000m).

A word on Nyles subgrid scale closure

$$\begin{aligned}
 \partial_t \vec{u} &= \boxed{-\vec{\omega} \times \vec{u}} - \vec{\nabla} \left(p + \frac{|\vec{u}|^2}{2} \right) + b\vec{k} && + \cancel{\nu \nabla^2 \vec{u}} \\
 &\quad \downarrow \epsilon_k && \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u} = 0 \\
 &\quad \text{(Dissipation of K)} && \\
 \partial_t b + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \boxed{(\vec{u}b)} &= 0 && + \cancel{\kappa_T \nabla^2 b} \\
 &\quad \downarrow \epsilon_\alpha \text{(Mixing)} &&
 \end{aligned}$$

- No Reynolds stress, no explicit closure.
- Vector-invariant form of the Boussinesq equations.
- Closure is brought implicitly by **upwind biased discretization**.
- There is no direct term for the dissipation of kinetic energy and mixing.
- No direct way to estimate dissipation rates.

Energy Framework

Thermostat

K : kinetic energy,
 E_a : Available potential energy,
 E_b : Background potential energy,

- We can compute all the energy fluxes.
- Defining the open control volume is key.

Open control Volume

We can estimate de dissipation!

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_t K &= \phi_z - \phi_p - \epsilon_k, \\ \partial_t E_a &= -\phi_z + \phi_b - \epsilon_a, \\ \partial_t E_b &= -\phi_b + \phi_e + \epsilon_a,\end{aligned} \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \begin{aligned}\epsilon_k &= \phi_z - \phi_p \\ \epsilon_a &= -\phi_z + \phi_b\end{aligned}$$

If $\partial_t K \approx 0$ and $\partial_t E_a \approx 0$

We can as well estimate de mixing efficiency

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\epsilon_a}{\epsilon_k + \epsilon_a} \quad \text{or} \quad \mathcal{E} = \frac{\phi_b - \phi_z}{\phi_b + \phi_p}$$

Energy reservoirs

- It reaches equilibrium after 4 days.
- APE is approximately constant after day 4.
- K remains constant during the whole simulation.

Energy fluxes

$$\overline{\phi_p} = 2.6 \times 10^{-7} m^2 s^{-3}$$

$$\overline{\phi_b} = 2.1 \times 10^{-6} m^2 s^{-3}$$

$$\overline{\phi_z} = 4.3 \times 10^{-7} m^2 s^{-3}$$

Dissipation

$$\overline{\epsilon_k} = 1.7 \times 10^{-7} m^2 s^{-3}$$

$$\overline{\epsilon_a} = 1.6 \times 10^{-6} m^2 s^{-3}$$

Flux comparisons

$$\frac{\phi_p}{\phi_z} \sim 0.6$$

$$\frac{\phi_z}{\phi_b} \sim 0.21$$

$$\frac{\epsilon_k}{\phi_z} \sim 0.4$$

$$\frac{\epsilon_a}{\phi_b} \sim 0.79$$

Mixing Efficiency

- We found that the **mixing efficiency is ~ 0.7** .

Conclusions

- The framework was useful to estimate dissipation rates and mixing efficiency.
- First implementation of this framework and is a test for Nyles.
- Ocean mixing efficiency is ~ 0.2 and in the plume is 0.7 .
- Compare de model with laboratory experiments or other numerical simulations.
- Repeat the experiment increasing the resolution.

Support slides

Mechanical injection flux

$$\phi_e = \phi(b_1 z_1 - b_0 z_0) - Q_b S_{\text{bot}} z_0 + \phi(p_r(z_1) - p_r(z_0))$$

\uparrow \uparrow \uparrow
 ϕ_{E_1} ϕ_{E_2} ϕ_{p_r}

Definitions

$$E_a = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \frac{(b - b_r(z))^2}{2N_r^2} dV \quad \text{and} \quad K = \frac{1}{2V} \int_V (u^2 + v^2 + w^2) dV$$

$\phi_z = \overline{(b - b_r)w}^V$ is volume integrated conversion from potential to kinetic energy

$\phi_b = \overline{Q(b - b_r)}^V / N^2$ is volume integrated APE generation term from the background potential energy due to the thermal forcing integrated over the volume

$\phi_p = \overline{w p^S}$ is input of potential energy associated with the forcing already described, and